

Acknowledgement

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Ligand Exchange Equilibria of Metal Complexes. Part-II. Extraction and Exchange Constants of Metal- α -benzoin Oximates in Chloroform†

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METAL chelates extracted by organic solvents can be converted into other metal chelates by the addition of a suitable chelating agent². Metal diphenylcarbazone in solution reacts with α -benzoin oxime liberating free diphenylcarbazone and form metal- α -benzoin oximate.

The equilibrium constant is related to the extraction constant of the metal chelate. Using the extraction constant, the equilibrium constant of an exchange can be calculated and vice versa.

Experimental

Diphenylcarbazones : Metal-diphenylcarbazones were prepared³ by shaking 1.0×10^{-3} M diphenylcarbazone (H_2Dp) in chloroform with excess aqueous metal salt solutions at desired pH values.

α -Benzoin oximates : Solid complexes of Ag, Tl^I, Cd, Zn, Cu, Ni and Co were prepared by refluxing α -benzoin oxime (HBo) and the metal salts in ethanolic solution. Solutions of 1.0×10^{-3} M metal- α -benzoin oximates were prepared in chloroform.

Thallium diphenylcarbazone, Tl(HDp), was prepared by shaking excess of aqueous solution of thallium(I) chloride at pH 7.0 with chloroform solution (1.0×10^{-3} M) of diphenylcarbazone.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of red coloured thallium diphenylcarbazone solution in chloroform shows a single strong band at 540 nm ($\epsilon = 3740 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$). When a chloroform solution of α -benzoin oxime is added to thallium diphenylcarbazone, α -benzoin oxime displaces diphenylcarbazone and equilibrium is reached within a few minutes. At equilibrium, the colour of the Tl(HDp) solution changes from red to faint pink,

for which the equilibrium constant,

$$E_{Tl(HDp)-HBo}^{org} = \frac{[Tl(Bo)]_{org}[H_2Dp]_{org}}{[Tl(HDp)]_{org}[HBo]_{org}}$$

The reversibility of the reaction is confirmed by mixing thallium- α -benzoin oximate with diphenylcarbazone. Similar procedure was adopted for confirming the reversibility of all the reactions studied in this work,

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL CONDITION EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF EXCHANGE REACTION (E), AND EXTRACTION CONSTANTS OF METAL-DITHIZONATES ($KM(HDz)_n$), METAL- α -BENZOIN OXIMATES, ($KM(Bo)_n$) AND METAL-DIPHENYLCARBAZONATES ($K(HDp)_n$) IN CHLOROFORM

Reaction	pH	λ_{max} nm	$\epsilon_{\lambda_{max}}$	log E (± 0.1)	log $KM(HDz)_n^*$	log $KM(Bo)_n$	log $KM(HDp)_n$
Tl(HDp) + HBo = Tl(Bo) + H ₂ Dp	7.0	540	8 740	-1.8	-3.80	-5.89	-4.09
Cd(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Cd(Bo) ₂ + H ₂ Dp	8.0	550	12 200	-2.5	0.50	-4.36	-1.88
Zn(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Zn(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	7.0	540	9 920	-2.3	1.0	-2.90	-0.63
Cu(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Cu(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	7.5	550	31 600	-2.4	8.70	2.20	4.57
Ni(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Ni(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	7.0	550	25 800	-1.1	2.46	-6.04	-4.97
Co(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Co(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	7.0	550	23 200	-1.7	-1.50	-7.98	-6.32
Pd(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Pd(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	2.3	570	3 200	-2.3	>27.0	>16.40	>18.68
Pb(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Pb(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	6.0	550	5 200	-2.3	-0.90	-7.85	-5.52

* Lit. value.

† Part-I, Ref. 1.

Equilibrium constant,

$$E_{\text{Ti(Bo)}-\text{H}_2\text{Dp}}^{\text{org}} = \frac{[\text{Ti(HDp)}]_{\text{org}}[\text{HBo}]_{\text{org}}}{[\text{Ti(Bo)}]_{\text{org}}[\text{H}_2\text{Dp}]_{\text{org}}}$$

The chloroform solution of, thallium diphenylcarbazone on treatment with varying amounts of the chloroform solution of α -benzoin oxime, immediately liberates diphenylcarbazone. Equilibrium concentrations of all the species involved are determined as follows.

From the extinction coefficient of the complex, Ti(HDp) , equilibrium concentration of Ti(HDp) is found out. The difference between the absorbance before and after the equilibration corresponds to the change in concentration of Ti(HDp) and also may be used to measure the concentration of Ti(Bo) formed in the reaction. The equilibrium concentration of diphenylcarbazone liberated in the reaction is indirectly calculated and is taken same as that of the concentration of Ti(Bo) formed. Exactly the same amount, i.e. $[\text{Ti(Bo)}]$ or $[\text{H}_2\text{Dp}]$ is consumed in the reaction and, therefore, the equilibrium concentration of HBo is taken as $\{[\text{HBo}]_{\text{org}}\} - \{[\text{H}_2\text{Dp}]_{\text{formed}}\}$. The experimental conditions and the values of the equilibrium constants of the exchange reactions in chloroform are summarised in Table 1. The results reveal that the equilibrium constants can be determined accurately.

The work with diphenylcarbazone is likely to be less reliable and less reproducible partly because of the lack of characteristic differences in spectral properties of the diphenylcarbazones and due to the lack of report on structure and properties of these complexes.

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Kinetic Evidence for Steric Enhancement of Resonance in Vanadium(v) and Lead Tetraacetate Oxidation of Substituted Phenyl Methyl Sulphides†

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THE phenomenon of steric enhancement of resonance¹ received substantial evidence from the work carried out by various workers². As a part of the extension of the programme on oxidation of some substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides by vanadium(v) and lead tetraacetate, we obtained kinetic

evidence for the said phenomenon. We report here our results on oxidation of some substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides with vanadium(v) and lead tetraacetate.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Acetic acid was purified over chromium trioxide. The substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides were prepared by known procedures³. Double-distilled water was used for all the purposes. The reactions were followed by estimating the unreacted vanadium(v) and lead tetraacetate using the procedures given elsewhere⁴.

Results and Discussion

The second order rate constants for the oxidation of substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides by vanadium(v) in aqueous acetic acid are presented in Table 1. The oxidation is facilitated by electron-donating groups in the benzene ring and is retarded by the electron-withdrawing ones.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF SOME SUBSTITUTED-PHENYL METHYL SULPHIDES BY VANADIUM(V)

Solvent = 50% aq. acetic acid, Temp. = 35°, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.1 \text{ M}$

Sulphide	k_a		$k_{\text{obs}}/k_{\text{calc}}$
	$\times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$		
	Obs.	Calc.	
Methyl phenyl (1)	6.32	—	—
Methyl m-tolyl (2)	12.62	—	—
4-Methoxyphenyl methyl (3)	3 320.0	—	—
4-Methoxy-3-methylphenyl methyl (4)	16 400.0	6 629.5	2.47
3,5-Dimethylphenyl methyl (5)	25.39	25.20	1.01
3,5-Dimethyl-4-methoxyphenyl methyl (6)	426.0	19 238.0	0.022

p-Methoxyphenyl methyl sulphide (3) undergoes oxidation about 500-times faster than methyl phenyl sulphide (1) due to greater electron density at the sulphur atom caused by the resonance interaction of the methoxy group with the reaction centre. The observed rate constant for the oxidation of 4-methoxy-3-methylphenyl methyl sulphide (4) is significantly higher than the value predicted on the basis of the additivity of group effects indicating that there is greater conjugative interaction of methoxy group with the reaction centre in 4 than in 3. This enhancement of resonance is due to the steric effect of 3-methyl group (*ortho* to OCH_3) which restricts the free rotation of methoxy group thereby increasing the probability of the latter to attain planarity with the benzene ring.

It is also of interest to note that 3,5-dimethyl-4-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphide (6) undergoes oxidation at a slower rate than 3. In fact, the ratio $k_{\text{obs}}/k_{\text{calc}}$ in the case of 6 is far less than unity indicating that there is expected steric inhibition of resonance in 6. Also, the ratio of $k_{\text{obs}}/k_{\text{calc}}$ in 3,5-dimethylphenyl methyl sulphide (5) is almost unity indicating that the effect of groups is additive.

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